

Dual governance and digital labor control: Algorithmic exploitation and structural alienation in Croatia's gig economy

Abstract

This article introduces the concept of *dual governance labor control* to explain how algorithmic management and third-party intermediaries jointly deepen precarity in platform capitalism. Drawing on Labor Process Theory and cyberpsychology, the analysis examines Croatia's food delivery sector as a diagnostic case of how digital infrastructures restructure power, fragment accountability, and intensify alienation. Based on surveys, focus groups, and interviews with delivery workers and union leaders, the study shows how opaque algorithms produce psychological strain and decision fatigue, while aggregators displace responsibility, racialise labour hierarchies, and undermine collective organisation. These dynamics reveal how class, migration, and digital control intersect to maximize surplus extraction while eroding workers' agency. In highlighting the structural and affective dimensions of this regime, the article extends labour process theory and situates algorithmic anxiety as a systemic outcome of capitalist governance. It concludes by outlining regulatory and collective strategies to contest dual governance and advance more democratic, transparent, and worker-centred alternatives in the platform economy.

Keywords

dual governance labor control, algorithmic management, gig economy, labor precarity, labor process theory

Non-Technical Summary

Background

Food delivery apps like Wolt, Bolt, and Glovo have become everyday services in Croatia. Yet behind the ease of ordering lies a workforce of couriers whose jobs are shaped by two forms of control: the platforms' algorithms and third-party "aggregators" who formally employ most couriers. This dual system fragments responsibility, increases insecurity, and places workers under constant stress, particularly in a post-socialist economy with weak labor protections.

Why was this study done?

The gig economy is promoted as modern and flexible, but for many it means unpredictable pay and long hours. In Croatia, where stable jobs are scarce and youth unemployment is high, thousands of young and migrant workers depend on food delivery. Still, little research has explored how platforms and aggregators jointly affect workers' lives. This study set out to answer two questions: (1) How do algorithms and aggregator companies shape couriers' conditions and well-being? and (2) What fairness and transparency concerns arise from this system?

What did the researcher do and find?

The research combined surveys with 29 delivery workers, four focus groups with unionized riders, and interviews with union leaders, carried out from late 2023 to 2024. Findings show that algorithms are a major source of stress. Couriers reported sudden changes in how tasks were assigned, unpredictable incomes, and penalties for rejecting deliveries, even when refusal was unavoidable. Workers described the experience as being "on call all day," leading to fatigue, anxiety, and feelings of powerlessness.

Aggregators add a second layer of control. By acting as intermediaries, they take a cut of wages, fragment the workforce, and make it harder to organize. When problems arise, platforms blame aggregators and vice versa, leaving workers stuck in between. Some aggregators were said to dissolve and re-open under new names to avoid accountability.

Tensions emerged between local and migrant workers. Many Croatian couriers felt that aggregators favored migrants who accepted lower pay, while migrants themselves often faced debt, exhausting hours, and broken promises. Both groups are exploited in different ways, but the system encourages division rather than solidarity.

What do these findings mean?

The study shows that food delivery in Croatia is not simply about flexibility but about a dual system that maximizes profits and minimizes accountability. Algorithms dictate work rhythms while aggregators diffuse responsibility, deepening precarity and stress.

For policy, this means regulation must target both platforms and aggregators together. Workers need the right to organize across both, and companies must be required to make algorithms transparent. Lessons from Spain's Rider Law or Italy's bias-detection initiatives are relevant, but Croatia's reliance on aggregators requires tailored reforms. For the wider public, the findings are a reminder that the convenience of app-based delivery has hidden human costs. Every order relies on workers navigating unpredictable systems, with little security and high psychological strain. Recognizing these realities can help push for fairer digital labor practices. The gig economy is less a story of freedom than of old patterns of labor exploitation repackaged through apps and middlemen. Addressing this requires not only new rules but also a broader commitment to protecting workers' dignity in the digital age.

“The worker feels at home only during his leisure time, whereas at work he feels homeless.”

— Karl Marx, Economic and Philosophic Manuscripts of 1844

In his 1930 essay *Economic Possibilities for our Grandchildren*, Keynes predicted a major expansion of the service sector by 2030 (Szabó-Szentgróti, Végvári, and Varga 2021). Rather than producing widespread prosperity, this expansion has unfolded under conditions of capitalist restructuring, where artificial intelligence (AI) and algorithmic management have become central mechanisms of labour control in the gig economy. This article examines the Croatian food delivery sector as an empirical case to analyse how algorithmic management and third-party intermediaries (“aggregators”) jointly structure labour control in platform work. While platform labour has been widely studied in other contexts, the Croatian case is characterised by the widespread use of aggregators, weak labour protections, and growing reliance on migrant workers. Together, these features intensify precarity and fragment responsibility in ways that are analytically distinctive.

To capture this layered system, the article introduces the concept of *dual governance labour control*. Under this model, platforms retain algorithmic control over task allocation, performance evaluation, and income flows, while intermediaries formally employ workers and absorb legal responsibility. This separation obscures accountability, diffuses power, and complicates collective organisation. Although the analysis is grounded in Croatia, similar arrangements can be observed across the post-Yugoslav region, where weak institutional

protections and the rapid expansion of platform work generate structural precarity (Andjelković et al. 2024).

Across Europe, delivery workers have staged strikes and protests against deteriorating conditions, including the shift from hourly pay to per-delivery compensation (Bulut and Yeşilyurt 2024). In Croatia, platforms such as Wolt, Bolt, and Glovo have dominated the market since 2018, displacing local businesses and reshaping urban service labour (Starčević 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated both demand for platform services and labour supply (Croatian Competition Agency 2021). Although marketed as flexible, these platforms rely on fragmented task allocation and competitive individualisation, eroding solidarity and increasing insecurity (Mrvos 2021; Christiaens 2022). In post-socialist contexts such as Croatia, these dynamics are intensified by labour market restructuring and weak enforcement mechanisms. The spread of aggregators adds an additional layer of governance, increasing opacity and further fragmenting accountability. Similar developments have been documented in Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, where informal courier work and discrimination against migrant workers from the Global South are widespread (Anđelković, Šapić and Skočajić 2019; Andjelković et al. 2024). These conditions generate what has been described as *algorithmic anxiety* (Elliott 2024), as opaque systems dictate pay, schedules, and ratings. Decision fatigue emerges as workers continuously adapt to shifting and non-transparent algorithmic criteria (Liu et al. 2024). Cyberpsychological research links such unpredictability to stress and cognitive overload, suggesting that these effects should be understood not as individual pathologies but as structurally produced outcomes of digital labour control (Tisseron 2018; Moore 2018; Casilli 2024). Aggregators intensify these pressures by distancing workers from platforms, imposing additional fees, and deepening informational asymmetries (Lu 2020; Vladislavljević and Kučinac 2023).

Labour Process Theory (LPT) provides a starting point for analysing these forms of labour control (Thompson 1989; Braverman 1998), but its traditional focus on industrial settings does not fully capture algorithmic governance. Recent scholarship calls for extending LPT to account for algorithmic opacity, digital abstraction, and affective dimensions of control (Gandini 2019; Veen, Barratt and Goods 2020). By integrating insights from cyberpsychology, this article examines how algorithmic management and aggregators jointly reinforce capitalist control in a peripheral post-socialist economy, producing both material precarity and psychological strain.

The study addresses two research questions:

- (1) How do algorithmic management and aggregator systems shape the working conditions and psychological well-being of food delivery workers in Croatia?
- (2) What fairness and transparency concerns arise in algorithmic task allocation under the aggregator model?

To answer these questions, the article draws on a mixed-methods study combining surveys, focus groups, and interviews. The findings highlight algorithmic unpredictability, aggregator-driven isolation, and the fragmentation of responsibility. The discussion situates these dynamics within debates on digital labour control and accountability, while the conclusion considers regulatory implications for platform work in the Croatian context.

Literature review

Research on platform labour has shown how algorithmic management reshapes labour control by replacing direct human supervision with automated systems of task allocation, performance

evaluation, and remuneration (Lee et al. 2015; Möhlmann and Zalmanson 2017). While digital platforms promote flexibility and autonomy, numerous studies demonstrate that algorithmic governance often produces dependency, opacity, and reduced worker agency (Rosenblat and Stark 2016; Aloisi and De Stefano 2022). Tasks are fragmented, competition is intensified, and responsibility for outcomes is increasingly displaced onto workers themselves.

In Croatia, systematic research on platform-mediated labour remains limited, despite the rapid expansion of food delivery platforms since 2018 (Smojver 2024). Existing regional studies nevertheless highlight how algorithmic management deepens precarity and exposes regulatory gaps, particularly in South-Eastern Europe (Aleksynska 2020; Ivanović et al. 2023; Anđelković, Jakobi and Radonjić 2024). Platforms prioritise efficiency and scalability over worker well-being, producing insecure, low-paid jobs that reflect broader patterns of labour market restructuring in post-socialist economies.

These dynamics align with Labour Process Theory (LPT), which conceptualises managerial control as a central feature of capitalist labour organisation (Thompson 1989; Braverman 1998). However, classical LPT was developed in the context of industrial workplaces and does not fully capture the abstraction, opacity, and automation characteristic of algorithmic governance. Recent scholarship therefore calls for extending LPT to account for digital forms of control, surveillance, and consent production in platform work (Gandini 2019; Veen, Barratt and Goods 2020). While the literature on algorithmic management has grown substantially, it often treats platforms as the primary locus of control, overlooking the role of intermediaries. In many platform economies, especially outside core Western contexts, labour relations are mediated by third-party companies that formally employ workers while platforms retain control over task allocation and income flows. Ursula Huws' concept of the "cybertariat" captures this broader restructuring of labour under digital capitalism, where value is extracted by disembedding work from stable employment and commodifying time, availability, and subjectivity (Huws 2014). The Croatian aggregator model reflects this logic: formal employment ties are weakened, while algorithmic command and availability-based control are intensified. Intermediaries charge fees, manage contracts, and absorb legal responsibility, allowing platforms to maintain an asset-light model while avoiding direct accountability. Empirical studies increasingly document how such arrangements deepen structural inequalities. Stark and Pais (2020) describe platforms as organisations that rely on externalised assets and labour while centralising control through algorithms. In the Croatian context, Vladislavljević and Kučinac (2023) show how aggregators extract fees with minimal support for workers, exacerbating insecurity and limiting avenues for redress. Yet the interaction between algorithmic management and intermediary governance remains under-theorised, particularly in post-socialist labour markets characterised by weak protections, fragmented unionisation, and limited enforcement capacity (Tomkiewicz 2018). This gap is especially salient in Croatia and neighbouring countries, where intermediaries play a central role in organising platform labour. Similar dynamics have been observed in Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, where informal courier work, reliance on migrant labour, and regulatory ambiguity intensify precarity (Anđelković, Šapić and Skočajić 2019; Anđelković et al. 2024). Existing research rarely analyses how these intermediary arrangements interact with algorithmic systems to produce layered forms of control and diffuse responsibility.

Beyond material conditions, scholars increasingly note the affective and psychological consequences of algorithmic labour control. Opaque systems governing pay, schedules, and task allocation generate uncertainty and cognitive strain, contributing to stress and reduced well-being among platform workers (Jhaver, Karpfen and Antin 2018; Jarrahi et al. 2021). Cyberpsychological research links such unpredictability to cognitive overload and decision fatigue, as workers must continuously adapt their behaviour to shifting and non-transparent criteria (Tisseron 2018; Moore 2018; Casilli 2024). The concept of *algorithmic anxiety* captures

these experiences as structurally produced outcomes rather than individual pathologies (Elliott 2024). In contexts where workers lack meaningful feedback, recourse mechanisms, or collective support, psychological strain becomes an integral component of labour control. Intermediaries can intensify these effects by further distancing workers from platforms, increasing informational asymmetries, and fragmenting communication channels (Lu 2020). While some studies document forms of resistance to algorithmic control, such as “algoactivism” (Weber, De Jong, and Remus 2023), empirical evidence from post-socialist contexts remains limited. Existing research suggests that fragmentation, competition, and intermediary governance often constrain collective mobilisation, reinforcing individualised coping strategies rather than coordinated resistance.

Drawing on Labour Process Theory and insights from cyberpsychology, this study addresses a gap in the literature by analysing how algorithmic management and intermediary governance jointly structure labour control in Croatia’s food delivery sector. By conceptualising this arrangement as dual governance labour control, the article links material precarity and affective strain to the interaction between algorithmic systems and intermediary employment models in a post-socialist context.

Methodology

This study adopts an exploratory qualitative research design. The aim is not to produce statistically representative findings, but to identify recurring patterns, experiences, and mechanisms shaping platform labour under algorithmic management and intermediary governance in Croatia. Fieldwork was conducted between November 2023 and September 2024. Data were collected using a combination of an online survey, focus groups, and semi-structured interviews. Sampling followed a convenience and snowball strategy, primarily through Facebook groups for delivery workers and contacts established via trade union activities. All participants provided informed consent, and all data were anonymised. The study draws on three complementary sources of data. First, an online survey was completed by 29 food delivery workers. The survey was used descriptively to map key experiences related to algorithmic management, perceived fairness, income unpredictability, and coping strategies. It adapted the Algorithmic Management Questionnaire (AMQ) to the Croatian context, incorporating locally relevant features such as aggregator-based employment, personal business licenses (*obrti*), and platform-specific work arrangements. The survey was administered bilingually (Croatian and English) to reflect the linguistic diversity of the workforce, and translations were reviewed by a bilingual proofreader.

Second, four focus groups were conducted with a small group of seven unionised delivery workers. These focus groups were held with the same participants across multiple sessions. This longitudinal approach allowed for sustained discussion and progressive refinement of themes rather than one-off data collection. Early focus groups focused primarily on algorithmic management and experiences of uncertainty and anxiety, and directly informed the design of the survey. Later sessions revealed the central role of aggregators in shaping labour conditions, contributing to the development of the article’s core concept of dual governance labour control.

Third, two semi-structured interviews were conducted with union leaders involved in organising platform workers. These interviews were used to provide an institutional and organisational perspective on platform labour, intermediary practices, and constraints on collective action. They are not treated as representative worker accounts, but as contextual and analytical material that complements workers’ narratives.

In addition to formal data collection, the author attended union meetings while coordinating platform labour projects for Novi Sindikat, an independent Croatian trade union active in the platform economy. Observations from these meetings informed the research context and interpretation of findings but are not treated as a separate dataset. Data from all three sources were analysed using thematic analysis. Coding focused on patterns related to labour control, opacity, fragmentation, perceptions of fairness, and psychological strain. Analysis was guided by Labour Process Theory, with concepts from cyberpsychology used to interpret affective and cognitive dimensions of algorithmic governance. Triangulation across methods strengthened analytical consistency and helped relate individual experiences to broader structural mechanisms.

Theoretical framework

This study is grounded in Labour Process Theory (LPT), which conceptualises labour control as a central mechanism through which capital organises work, extracts surplus value, and disciplines labour (Thompson 1989; Braverman 1998). LPT provides the primary analytical framework for examining how algorithmic management and intermediary arrangements structure work in the platform economy. To capture the affective consequences of these arrangements, the analysis draws secondarily on concepts from cyberpsychology, which are used to interpret how structurally imposed forms of control are experienced at the level of subjectivity. Within this framework, *dual governance labour control* refers to a system in which labour is simultaneously governed by algorithmic management and intermediary employment arrangements. Platforms retain control over task allocation, performance evaluation, and income flows through opaque algorithmic systems, while aggregators formally employ workers, manage contracts, and absorb legal responsibility. This division fragments accountability, obscures managerial intent, and limits workers' capacity for contestation. Rather than optimising efficiency alone, algorithmic systems function as instruments of labour discipline, particularly in post-socialist contexts characterised by weak labour protections and limited enforcement.

Building on Braverman's analysis of deskilling, this study extends LPT to algorithmic oversight, where fragmentation and abstraction are mediated through code rather than direct supervision. Thompson's insights into surveillance and consent remain relevant, as algorithmic systems conceal managerial decisions while enforcing discipline automatically. Stark and Pais (2020) describe platforms as asset-light infrastructures that externalise risk while centralising control; this logic is extended here to aggregators, which further diffuse responsibility by inserting contractual buffers between workers and platforms. In this sense, aggregators amplify digital control by mediating employment while leaving algorithmic authority intact. To interpret the subjective effects of these structural arrangements, the framework draws on cyberpsychological concepts such as algorithmic anxiety and decision fatigue. Algorithmic anxiety refers to a persistent state of uncertainty produced by opaque systems governing pay, scheduling, ratings, and access to work. Decision fatigue captures the cognitive strain associated with continuously adapting to shifting, non-transparent criteria under conditions of constant availability. These experiences are treated not as individual pathologies but as predictable outcomes of digitally mediated labour control, consistent with Marxist accounts of alienation and contemporary analyses of cybernetic labour extraction (Dyer-Witford 2015; Pasquinelli 2019; Jarrahi et al. 2021).

The Croatian case illustrates how these dynamics are intensified in a post-socialist context shaped by neoliberal restructuring, weak institutional protections, and fragmented labour markets. Workers are separated not only from the products of their labour but also from the labour process itself and from possibilities of collective organisation. By integrating LPT with

cyberpsychological insights, this framework enables an analysis of how algorithmic management and intermediary governance jointly fragment worker agency, deepen precarity, and suppress collective resistance. The empirical analysis that follows applies this framework to examine how dual governance labour control operates in practice in Croatia's food delivery sector.

Results

The results presented below are organized to foreground both structural and psychological dimensions of labor control, as experienced by workers – not as isolated stress responses, but as systemic effects of platform and aggregator governance. This section presents findings that respond to both central research questions: how dual governance systems affect worker conditions and well-being, and how workers perceive algorithmic fairness. The results are structured around key emergent themes, including perceived favoritism, unpredictability, and psychological strain. The survey respondents were predominantly aged between 25 and 34, highlighting a younger workforce within Croatia's gig economy. This age group represents a critical demographic in the Croatian labor market, where unemployment among young adults (aged 15–29) is about 19% (“Croatia: Youth Unemployment Rate” 2024), among the highest in the European Union. Such figures underscore why gig work remains an attractive option for younger workers seeking income opportunities amidst limited job prospects.

Demographics and employment status

The survey respondents were predominantly aged between 25 and 34 (56%), followed by those aged 18–24 (28%), while only a small share were 35 or older (16%). This age group constitutes the majority of the delivery workers surveyed, reflecting a younger workforce. Only a small percentage of respondents were older than 45, highlighting the demographic concentration in younger age brackets. A significant majority of respondents were male (86.2%), while female workers accounted for only 13.8% of the sample.

Most participants speak Croatian as their native language, with some variations. The predominant nationality is Croatian, though there is a noticeable presence of international workers, notably from India and North Macedonia. This demographic composition aligns with the survey results showing that 82.8% of respondents work for aggregators, indicating that a younger, male-dominated, and culturally diverse workforce is navigating the highly competitive gig economy. Additionally, 17.2% of the respondents are self-employed, reflecting the two primary legal models for the platform economy in Croatia. With this demographic overview in mind, we now turn to their engagement with platforms and work patterns to better understand the nature of their employment.

Platform engagement and work patterns

The data reveal that Wolt is the most popular platform among the surveyed workers, with 82.8% engaged through it. A substantial share have been in delivery work for at least two years, indicating a mix of experienced and newer workers. Many respondents reported working more than 40 hours a week, and for most (75.9%) this job serves as their primary source of income. At the same time, the distribution of working hours is highly varied, suggesting that while some treat delivery as part-time, others depend on it as full-time employment – underscoring the job's inherent unpredictability. While flexibility and income are key motivators for workers, the experience of engaging with algorithmic management reveals deeper challenges.

Motivations and contradictions of gig work

The motivations to join these platforms are largely tied to flexible working hours (96.6%) and independence in work (58.6%). Workers also mentioned additional income (34.5%), a high

primary source of income (27.6%), recommendation from friends or family (17.2%), interest in technology and new forms of work (13.8%), and flexibility while studying (3.4%). However, the responses indicate that algorithmic management significantly affects these motivations. One participant expressed frustration, stating, *“Algorithms prefer couriers who work much more than full-time hours”* (Survey Respondent 28, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 25–34, Wolt, 2/22/2024). Another highlighted issues with fairness, saying, *“Changes in the algorithm mean that I’ll have a harder time earning what I need”* (Survey Respondent 29, delivery worker, male, North Macedonian age 56–64, Glovo/Wolt, 4/5/2024).

These quotes emphasize the lack of transparency and fairness, where many workers feel that algorithms prioritize newer, often international, workers over more experienced local ones. Such challenges are compounded by the impacts of algorithmic management, which deeply affect workers' well-being and sense of control.

Well-being, control, and mental strain

Algorithmic management significantly affects the mental health of Croatian gig workers, particularly through its unpredictable task assignments, income variability, and penalty mechanisms. Workers frequently described feelings of stress, anxiety, and powerlessness. One respondent stated, *“Mentally and physically it gets worse because it’s like being on call all day for 60€ gross,”* (Survey Respondent 3, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 25–34, Glovo/Wolt, 2/22/2024), illustrating the continuous strain of work. Decision fatigue emerges as a prominent stressor, as workers must make constant adjustments to align with the algorithm’s unpredictable demands. This is compounded by the cognitive burden of interpreting opaque performance metrics and anticipating shifts in algorithmic preferences. A respondent highlighted this sense of unpredictability: *“The algorithm changes suddenly, and there’s no explanation. One day, I’m getting enough tasks; the next day, it feels like I’m invisible”*, (Focus Group Participant 1, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 28–34, Wolt, 6/27/2024)

Similarly, the penalization of task refusals exacerbates the pressure: *“If I refuse a delivery, like when I need to refuel, I’m immediately punished”* (Survey Respondent 8, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 35–44, Wolt, 2/22/2024). These opaque systems amplify what workers perceive as a loss of control. While algorithmic management is marketed as offering autonomy, workers repeatedly emphasized the illusion of flexibility. A respondent noted, *“I can choose when to work, but realistically, I have to follow peak times to earn decently”* (Survey Respondent 29, delivery worker, male, North Macedonian age 56–64, Glovo/Wolt, 4/5/2024).

This misalignment between perceived autonomy and the platform's control fosters "algorithmic anxiety" as workers struggle to predict earnings and schedules. In addition to the psychological strain, workers also face significant inequities in task allocation, particularly in relation to foreign worker policies.

Perceived disparities and the role of foreign worker policies

Perceived inequities in task allocation were a significant source of frustration for Croatian delivery workers, particularly in relation to foreign workers employed through aggregators. Many workers expressed concerns about perceived favoritism, with one commenting, *“I stand in front of a restaurant for 20 minutes, waiting for a task, and then a Nepali comes from somewhere and picks it up”* (Survey Respondent 4, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 25–34, Wolt, 2/22/2024). These experiences fuel the classic narrative of *“foreigners stealing our jobs,”* (Focus Group Participant 3, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 28–34, Glovo, 6/29/2024), but this perspective was not universally shared. Some workers recognized that foreign gig workers, like their Croatian counterparts, are simply seeking better opportunities. *“They’re just trying to survive, like we do when we go abroad,”* one respondent noted (Focus Group Participant 5,

delivery worker, male, Croat, age 34–40, Glovo/Wolt, 6/29/2024), highlighting a shared struggle rather than a divisive competition. While resentment was common, several participants expressed empathy toward foreign workers during focus group discussions, reflecting a dual discourse: one that acknowledges shared exploitation while also perceiving foreign workers as recipients of preferential treatment. This ambivalence reveals how aggregators may use nationality as a lever to fragment worker solidarity, an insight echoed in the discussion on alienation and disempowerment. As one Croatian courier explained, even foreign workers are often victims of a system that exploits everyone differently:

“The algorithm and its parameters are chaotically adjusted to push local couriers off the platform and to exploit foreign workers to the maximum so that certain individuals can profit. It’s nothing like it was before foreigners arrived – foreigners brought in by favored aggregators who are now making big money off them, along with some individuals from Wolt. Local couriers are discriminated against, and foreign workers are deceived, having been promised something completely different. As some leave, others arrive in this so-called ‘promised land,’ taking out loans of up to €5,000 to come here – only to be cheated. Pay-per-delivery has been rolled back to 2019 rates and is now even lower. Delivering for €1.75 today is disgraceful – especially considering that in 2019, when everything was 50% cheaper, the lowest-paid delivery was 14.70 kuna. So much for the algorithm. Everything is done manually, and couriers are exploited to the maximum. They’re offering deliveries 9 km away for €2.45. It’s appalling – what else is there to say?” (*Survey Respondent 12, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 45–54, Wolt, 2/23/2024*)

Another worker echoed this sentiment, directing criticism not at the foreign workers themselves but at the system that over-recruits and overworks them:

“It’s not so much the algorithm that affects us, but the unnecessary hiring of cheap labor and the constant violation of the law by aggregators when it comes to their working hours. They work 12 hours every day” (Survey Respondent 4, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 25–34, Wolt, 2/22/2024). Many workers expressed indeed concerns about perceived favoritism toward foreign workers employed through aggregators. In the survey, eight respondents explicitly raised the issue, and all unionized riders who participated in focus groups echoed the same concern. One worker noted, *“Based on acceptance rates, lately local workers have been given secondary priority while foreigners receive better deliveries”* (Survey Respondent 3, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 25–34, Glovo/Wolt, 2/22/2024). Another remarked, *“The algorithm and its parameters are chaotically adjusted to push out local delivery workers, maximizing the exploitation of foreigners”* (Survey Respondent 12, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 45–54, Wolt, 2/23/2024). A third added, *“Foreigners have priority, while we wait an hour or two for deliveries”* (Survey Respondent 22, delivery worker, female, Croat, age 35–44, Bolt, 2/25/2024). While both groups face similar challenges in terms of unpredictability and job insecurity, the experience of foreign workers may differ due to their temporary migration status or aspirations to move into more stable work. For many foreign workers, platform work may be viewed as a transitional phase, while Croatian workers, dealing with the limited availability of other stable work opportunities, often see gig work as a more permanent source of income.

The real issue, as some workers identified, lies in the aggregator system and its exploitation of vulnerable labor. Aggregators act as intermediaries, recruiting foreign workers under conditions that make their labor cheaper. This dynamic creates structural inequalities that pit workers against one another. As one union leader explained, *“Aggregators and platforms profit by creating competition between workers. They pay foreign workers less, and this undercuts wages for everyone”* (Union Leader 1, male, Croat, age 65–74, 3/10/2024). This situation mirrors

findings in Serbia, where aggregators (termed agencies) were revealed to enforce discriminatory practices against foreign workers, limiting their ability to choose tasks and restricting transparency about earnings. Research by investigative journalists at *Mašina* (2024) uncovered that foreign workers, often from India, were paid fixed, lower wages through agreements with agencies. This practice not only undercut local workers by reducing their earning opportunities, but also left Indian workers themselves vulnerable to exploitation, as they were tied to agency contracts with little bargaining power. While the payment algorithms used by Croatian platforms remain a business secret, anecdotal evidence suggests similar practices may be occurring. During focus groups, workers reported instances where, despite being closer to a restaurant, they would not receive a task, while foreign workers, positioned farther away, would be selected for delivery assignments. This pattern was explained by the workers as a result of foreign workers accepting lower wages, which made them more likely to be assigned tasks by the algorithm, even when it was less efficient to do so. Such arrangements highlight systemic exploitation enabled by weak regulation and the opaque nature of algorithmic management. These systemic inequities are further exacerbated by the aggregator model, which introduces additional layers of control and isolation.

The aggregator model: structural inequities and isolation

Aggregators play a critical role in shaping the experiences of gig workers in Croatia's platform economy. Acting as intermediaries between workers and platforms, aggregators introduce additional layers of control, exacerbating existing inequalities and fragmenting the workforce. This section explores three key dimensions of how aggregators impact workers: task allocation inequities, workforce isolation, and accountability gaps.

A prominent theme among surveyed workers was the perceived inequity in how tasks are distributed. Many workers expressed frustration with what they see as favoritism toward foreign workers employed by aggregators. One worker shared their experience of waiting for a task outside a restaurant, only to see a foreign worker assigned the job, even though they were farther away. Workers believed this was due to foreign workers accepting lower pay, which made them more likely to receive tasks—creating a sense of injustice among local workers. This perception of inequity fueled tensions, with workers questioning the fairness of the system that seemed to prioritize cost-saving over equitable practices. These tensions are not limited to Croatian delivery workers, as similar practices have been documented in Serbia, where foreign workers are often assigned tasks under less favorable conditions, including lower fixed wages and limited task visibility (Mašina 2024). Some workers blamed foreign workers for driving down wages and reducing task availability, a narrative that aligns with the broader "foreigners stealing our jobs" trope. However, other workers acknowledged that these inequities are systemic, driven by aggregator agreements that exploit vulnerable labor. As one worker remarked, foreign workers, like their Croatian counterparts, are in the gig economy out of necessity. They emphasized that such shared hardships are exacerbated by the practices of aggregators, who exploit lower wages, creating competition that pits workers against each other.

Aggregators fragment the workforce by dividing workers into smaller groups, often based on employment arrangements. This fragmentation prevents meaningful collective action and weakens workers' ability to negotiate better conditions. A union leader highlighted this issue, stating, "*Aggregators divide workers into silos – it's impossible to organize when everyone is tied to a different middleman*" (Union Leader 2, male, Croat, age 65–74, 6/27/2024).

This structural isolation is compounded by aggregators' practices of prioritizing short-term profitability over long-term worker well-being. By acting as intermediaries, aggregators dilute responsibility for labor conditions, further isolating workers from the platforms that ultimately dictate work policies. This dual-layered system of control leaves workers feeling disconnected

from both their employers and their peers. This collaboration also revealed the constrained role of unions under dual governance, where aggregators dilute collective bargaining potential by distancing workers from the platforms that ultimately control conditions of labor.

Workers frequently described feeling "trapped" between platforms and aggregators, with neither party taking responsibility for issues such as pay disputes or task assignments. One worker shared, *"If the algorithm fails me, the aggregator says it's the platform's fault. If my pay is wrong, they both blame each other"* (Focus Group Participant 2, delivery worker, female, Croat, age 33–39, Bolt, 6/27/2024). This lack of accountability exacerbates worker stress and frustration, as they are left with no effective means of resolving grievances.

Aggregators often operate with minimal oversight, exploiting legal loopholes to avoid scrutiny. In Croatia, workers noted that some aggregators dissolve and reestablish under new names, allowing them to evade accountability while perpetuating exploitative practices. This mirrors findings from Serbia, where similar patterns have been observed (Mašina 2024). The aggregator model in Croatia's gig economy intensifies structural inequities and isolates workers, creating a system where competition and fragmentation undermine solidarity. These structural challenges force workers to adapt in creative ways, but their strategies often reveal the limitations of individual responses to systemic problems.

Coping strategies and recommendations

These findings align with insights from cyberpsychology (Khadse et al. 2023), which explores how digital environments affect cognition, behavior, and affect. Algorithmic management systems—particularly when opaque and unpredictable—are known to produce cognitive overload, learned helplessness, and chronic anxiety, as workers are subjected to fluctuating and non-transparent feedback loops with little to no control over outcomes. This unpredictability mirrors the "variable ratio reinforcement schedule" found in addictive technologies, where intermittent and algorithmically controlled rewards (e.g., tasks, income) create psychological dependency while undermining rational planning and autonomy. In the context of dual governance, these effects are intensified: aggregators blur lines of accountability and further reduce transparency, compounding the sense of disempowerment. By framing algorithmic anxiety through cyberpsychological theory, the article highlights how digitally mediated labor systems not only degrade material conditions but also induce mental stress that fragments worker agency and discourages collective resistance.

In response to these stressors, workers adopt coping strategies that reflect both adaptation and constraint. These include optimizing availability around peak hours, avoiding task rejections to maintain algorithmic favor, and using multiple platforms simultaneously to hedge against downtime. Such strategies are rational responses to opaque systems but also reveal a normalization of algorithmic control, where workers internalize and adjust to technological discipline rather than challenge its premises. These everyday adaptations underscore the need to recognize platform labor not only as an economic condition but also as a psychological regime of control.

Many workers adjust their availability during peak hours to optimize earnings. By being available during periods of high demand, workers can minimize idle time and maximize task allocation. This adjustment aims to counteract the earnings unpredictability imposed by algorithmic task assignment. As one respondent described, *"Predictable working hours, not rejecting orders. Waiting before rush hour near restaurants"* (Survey Respondent 13, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 25–34, Wolt, 2/23/2024), which highlights a tactical approach to managing algorithmic volatility.

To mitigate dependence on a single platform's algorithm, some workers operate across multiple delivery apps. This diversification helps them maintain consistent work, especially if one platform is slow. One worker noted, *"Sometimes I use 2 platforms at the same time and choose the task that suits me better. This way I increase the likelihood of getting a task"* (Focus Group Participant 7, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 28–34, Bolt/Wolt, 7/15/2024). This approach reflects a workaround for the lack of control that algorithms impose, allowing workers to retain a degree of agency over their task load. Additionally, workers often optimize their work locations by positioning themselves in high-demand areas, increasing their chances of being assigned tasks. This tactic illustrates how workers anticipate and adapt to algorithmic preferences. One worker shared, *"I try to adapt by staying in parts of the city that I know and where there are more restaurants"* (Focus Group Participant 6, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 28–34, Glovo, 7/15/2024), emphasizing spatial strategy as a means to cope with the algorithm's unpredictable task distribution.

To maintain their algorithmic "standing," many workers avoid rejecting tasks, hoping this will lead to more stable assignments. This compliance-based approach demonstrates how workers perceive the algorithm as requiring continuous positive engagement. As one worker stated, *"Not rejecting orders"* (Survey Respondent 13, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 25–34, Wolt, 2/23/2024), revealing how workers actively adjust their behavior to conform to algorithmic expectations. Given the psychological toll of unpredictable schedules and task demands, some workers take breaks to manage stress and prevent burnout. One respondent expressed this as, *"Patience and only patience, waiting for orders"* (Survey Respondent 17, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 35–44, Glovo, 2/27/2024), underscoring the need for self-care practices amid the high demands of platform work.

Lastly, many workers attempt to resolve algorithmic issues by contacting platform support, though their experiences reveal significant shortcomings in these systems. One worker stated, *"Support staff cling to their explanations and direct us to the work of the algorithm"* (Focus Group Participant 2, delivery worker, female, Croat, age 33–39, Bolt, 6/27/2024). Another observed, *"The platform only tells us the algorithm is meant to be fair for everyone. That's all they say"* (Survey Respondent 25, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 25–34, Bolt/Wolt, 2/26/2024). These exchanges illustrate the workers' frustration with the lack of transparency and responsiveness from platform support.

While these coping mechanisms demonstrate workers' adaptability, they also underscore the urgent need for systemic reforms.

Worker calls for transparency and fairness

While these coping strategies show how workers try to adapt, they also highlight the futility of navigating a system governed by opaque algorithms that disregard their needs. Many workers emphasized the need for transparency, noting that frequent algorithm changes add confusion and further strain. One respondent reflected on the unpredictability, *"When the algorithm changes how it assigns deliveries, my workday can become quite tangled"* (Survey Respondent 29, delivery worker, male, North Macedonian age 56–64, Glovo/Wolt, 4/5/2024), while another highlighted the urgent need for regulatory oversight: *"Transparency of the platform and regulation of work so that there is work for everyone"* (Survey Respondent 3, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 25–34, Glovo/Wolt, 2/22/2024).

The widespread dissatisfaction with algorithmic opacity reinforces Labor Process Theory's insights into the digital transformation of labor, where control mechanisms intensify power imbalances and reduce worker autonomy. Algorithmic management in this context not only increases workers' stress and frustration but also enforces a model where workers feel

subordinate to impersonal and fluctuating criteria. As one worker explained: “It’s like living on call all day. You don’t know how much you’ll earn or when the next task will come – it’s exhausting” (Survey Respondent 4, delivery worker, male, Croat, age 25–34, Wolt, 2/22/2024). Another noted: “I feel like the algorithm has all the power. It’s frustrating because I can’t understand how it decides who gets more tasks” (Survey Respondent 29, delivery worker, male, North Macedonian, age 56–64, Glovo/Wolt, 4/5/2024). This study points to the necessity for platform companies to implement transparency in decision-making and fairer policies that genuinely address workers' mental well-being and financial security, potentially creating a healthier work environment in the growing digital economy. The Discussion returns to the article’s two guiding questions, linking empirical findings to theoretical reflections on alienation, control, and the digital intensification of labor exploitation. Psychological impacts are not treated as isolated symptoms but as structural consequences of fragmented, opaque governance.

Discussion

This study demonstrates how algorithmic management and third-party intermediaries jointly structure labour control in Croatia’s food delivery sector. Grounded in Labour Process Theory (Thompson 1989; Braverman 1998), the analysis confirms that digital capitalism intensifies labour control and surplus value extraction, while also revealing the limits of classic LPT when applied to platform-mediated work. By introducing the concept of dual governance labour control, the article shows how algorithmic systems and aggregators operate together to fragment accountability, isolate workers, and deepen precarity in ways that cannot be explained by algorithmic management alone. Marx’s concept of alienation remains central to understanding these dynamics. In the Croatian case, workers are estranged not only from the products of their labour, but from the conditions and rules governing it. Algorithmic management embeds control in opaque technical systems that regulate access to work, income, and time, while aggregators further distance workers from decision-making authority through contractual mediation. This produces a layered form of alienation that is both material and epistemic: workers are subordinated to systems they cannot fully see, understand, or contest. As analyses of cybernetic labour extraction suggest (Dyer-Witheford 2015; Pasquinelli 2019), digital infrastructures extend capitalist abstraction by transforming labour into fragmented, code-responsive inputs, while intermediaries absorb legal responsibility without relinquishing control.

The Croatian context sharpens these dynamics. High youth unemployment, weak collective bargaining structures, and fragmented labour protections create conditions in which platform work becomes a long-term livelihood rather than a transitional activity. Within this setting, aggregators flourish as mechanisms for externalising risk and diffusing accountability. While algorithmic management already constrains autonomy, the addition of intermediaries produces a dual governance structure in which neither platforms nor aggregators fully assume responsibility for labour conditions. This configuration intensifies dependence, uncertainty, and isolation, making resistance and collective organisation more difficult.

Table 1 provides an analytical mapping of these dynamics through the lens of Labour Process Theory, clarifying how algorithmic management and aggregator governance function as complementary mechanisms of labour control. Rather than presenting new empirical material, the table offers an interpretive synthesis that situates the findings within established LPT categories, highlighting how digital abstraction and contractual fragmentation jointly reorganise control, consent, and alienation under platform capitalism.

Table 1. Analytical mapping of dual governance labour control through Labour Process Theory
(*Interpretive synthesis based on the results presented above*)

Aspect of Findings	LPT Application
Control Over Work	Algorithmic management dictates task assignments and schedules, reducing worker control.
Task Fragmentation	Tasks are broken into smaller units, causing fragmentation and loss of coherence.
Surveillance	Constant monitoring via app metrics and evaluations increases surveillance.
Deskilling	Simplification and standardization of tasks lead to deskilling.
Worker Autonomy	Algorithmic control and lack of transparency reduce worker autonomy.
Psychological Impact	Unpredictable workloads and opaque management increase stress and anxiety.

Although empirically situated in Croatia, these dynamics resonate with research from other contexts where platformisation intersects with subcontracting and migration. Studies of platform labour in Latin America, South Asia, and Western Europe similarly document how intermediary arrangements and algorithmic control combine to weaken protections and fragment workforces. The Croatian case should therefore be understood not as an outlier, but as a particularly visible instance of a broader tendency within contemporary capitalism, in which labour control is increasingly exercised through dispersed technical and contractual mechanisms rather than direct managerial supervision. By extending LPT with cyberpsychological concepts such as algorithmic anxiety and decision fatigue, this study situates mental strain as the affective register of material disempowerment. Psychological stress emerges not as an individual coping failure, but as the lived expression of alienation under dual governance. Workers are required to continuously anticipate opaque algorithmic decisions, adapt to uncertainty, and manage risk in the absence of clear rules or recourse. Linking these affective experiences to labour process restructuring strengthens LPT's capacity to account for the embodied and emotional consequences of digital control.

From a regulatory perspective, the findings underscore the limits of reforms that focus exclusively on platforms while leaving intermediaries unaddressed. Where responsibility is split between algorithmic systems and aggregators, accountability gaps persist and enforcement becomes difficult. The Croatian case illustrates how intermediary-based models can undermine the intent of labour protections by redistributing risk rather than eliminating it. More broadly, the analysis suggests that addressing precarity in platform work requires confronting the combined operation of digital and contractual forms of control, rather than treating algorithmic management as a standalone problem.

Policy recommendations

As highlighted in existing scholarship, transparency, fair remuneration, and the right to collective organisation are central to addressing systemic exploitation in platform labour. However, the findings of this study show that such measures are insufficient when applied to platforms alone. The dual governance structure created by platforms and aggregators introduces a specific obstacle to collective action: control over task allocation, wages, and working conditions is distributed across two formally separate entities, while workers lack a unified counterpart against which to organise. Under this arrangement, platforms and aggregators sustain labour control by maintaining organisational separation and shifting responsibility between them. Workers are positioned as either “platform workers” or “aggregated workers,” a division that fragments collective identity and weakens bargaining power. From a labour process perspective, this fragmentation is not incidental but functional: it limits workers' capacity to confront capital by dispersing control across technical and contractual layers. Addressing precarity in such a system therefore requires interventions that treat platforms and aggregators as a single, integrated regime of labour control.

A feasible regulatory response lies in the principle of joint responsibility. Labour law could be reoriented to recognise platforms and aggregators as jointly accountable for earnings, task allocation, and working conditions, regardless of formal contractual arrangements. This would prevent responsibility-shifting and create a clear counterpart for collective bargaining. Crucially, the right to organise and bargain collectively should apply across both layers of governance, enabling workers and unions to negotiate with platforms and aggregators simultaneously rather than separately. In practical terms, this could involve requiring platforms and aggregators to jointly recognise trade unions and engage in collective negotiations as a condition for market operation. Collective agreements would then cover algorithmic

management practices, remuneration structures, and basic labour protections, including limits on working time and mechanisms for contesting automated decisions. Such an approach does not assume the abolition of platform work, but intervenes directly in the balance of power by restoring workers' collective capacity within a fragmented labour process.

These measures do not eliminate exploitation but constrain its most opaque and disempowering forms. By closing the institutional gap created by dual governance, joint accountability would weaken capital's ability to externalise risk, obscure control, and suppress collective organisation. Rather than treating algorithmic management as a technical problem or aggregators as neutral intermediaries, this approach recognises them as integral components of contemporary labour domination and targets them accordingly.

Limitations

While this study provides valuable insights into the impact of algorithmic management on food delivery workers in Croatia, several limitations should be acknowledged:

The sample size of 29 workers and focus groups with union members is consistent with qualitative research standards, which prioritize depth of insight over statistical generalizability. Studies have demonstrated that qualitative data saturation often occurs within small sample sizes, particularly when participant experiences are highly contextualized or when the phenomenon under investigation is tightly focused. In the nascent field of gig work studies in Croatia, the small sample enables a nuanced exploration of algorithmic management and aggregator dynamics. While union-centric recruitment may limit the representativeness of non-unionized perspectives, this approach ensures access to workers directly engaged in advocacy, offering critical insights into the dual-layered control systems shaping labor conditions. Future research should build on this foundation by incorporating diverse worker populations and expanding geographic coverage. The study did not systematically collect data on race, disability, or other intersectional identifiers, which limits its ability to explore how overlapping axes of marginalization affect workers' experiences. Future work should address these dimensions more explicitly. The study was geographically limited to Croatia, which may influence the applicability of the findings to other regions with different socio-economic and regulatory contexts. Comparative studies across different countries could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the issue.

The reliance on self-reported data from surveys and interviews may introduce bias, as participants may underreport or overreport their experiences due to social desirability or recall bias. Future studies could incorporate objective data from platform companies to complement self-reported measures. The rapidly evolving nature of digital platforms and algorithmic management systems means that the findings of this study may quickly become outdated. Ongoing research is necessary to keep pace with technological advancements and their impacts on workers.

Conclusion

This study extends Labour Process Theory by introducing the concept of dual governance labour control to explain how algorithmic management and intermediary employment arrangements jointly structure labour control in platform work. Drawing on the Croatian food delivery sector, the analysis shows that labour precarity is not produced by algorithmic systems alone, but by their interaction with aggregators that fragment accountability, externalise risk, and weaken collective organisation. In post-socialist contexts marked by weak institutional protections and labour market insecurity, this configuration intensifies exploitation and limits workers' capacity to contest control.

The Croatian case illustrates how post-digital capitalism operates at the semi-periphery of the European labour market. Here, digital platforms no longer function as disruptive innovations, but as stabilised infrastructures of labour domination. Algorithmic management becomes a normalised mode of governance, while aggregators act as outsourced institutions of control that allow platforms to scale without assuming responsibility for working conditions. Although similar arrangements exist in more regulated economies, Croatia makes visible the underlying logic of this model by exposing how legal ambiguity, subcontracting, and algorithmic opacity combine to reproduce alienation under contemporary capitalism. By integrating cyberpsychological concepts such as algorithmic anxiety and decision fatigue into LPT, the study demonstrates that mental strain is not an incidental side-effect of platform work, but an affective expression of structural disempowerment. Psychological stress emerges from workers' continuous efforts to navigate opaque systems, anticipate automated decisions, and manage uncertainty without meaningful recourse. This reframing situates affective experience as a constitutive dimension of labour control, rather than an individual coping failure, and extends LPT's analytical reach to the embodied consequences of digital governance. Comparable tensions between formal fairness frameworks and workers' lived experiences of cognitive strain have also been identified in related research on algorithmic labour benchmarking, where standardised evaluation principles fail to capture the affective and organisational consequences of opaque digital work systems (Author, anonymised manuscript).

From a regulatory perspective, the findings caution against approaches that address platforms while leaving intermediaries untouched. Where labour control is distributed across algorithmic and contractual layers, platform-centred regulation risks reproducing accountability gaps rather than closing them. Addressing precarity in platform work therefore requires recognising platforms and aggregators as a single regime of labour control and reasserting collective rights across both layers. While the Croatian case is context-specific, the dynamics it reveals are increasingly relevant across post-socialist and other peripheral economies where platformisation intersects with subcontracting and labour migration.

Future research could build on this framework by examining dual governance arrangements across sectors and national contexts, as well as by tracing the long-term effects of algorithmic management on workers' agency and collective capacity. More broadly, the study underscores that confronting exploitation in digital labour requires not only technical regulation, but a renewed focus on power, accountability, and collective organisation in the political economy of contemporary capitalism.

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